

deeco

dynamic energy, emissions
and cost optimization

a high-resolution exergy-services
supply modeling environment
used to evaluate
sustainability improvements

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Issue A

deeco is a versatile UNIX-based modeling environment which can help support the transformation to more sustainable energy systems.

Overview

deeco can be thought of as a *virtual laboratory* — a venue for investigating improvements to the systems that supply exergy-services — with the aim of reducing unsustainable outcomes in a cost-effective manner.

deeco can be applied to a wide range of problems — these applications may appear diverse but they are analytically similar:

- the **integrated assessment** of national and local operational **energy policy** — the term 'operational' indicates support for on-the-ground programs as opposed to long-range projections
- **additionality appraisal** under Kyoto CDM (clean development) and JI (joint implementation) mechanisms and related domestic initiatives
- single-operator **scheme design** support where sustainability gains are also sought

deeco is particularly suited (but not limited) to investigations that involve:

- **interacting modifications** — which may give rise to significant counteraction effects

- **staged upgrades** — particularly where sunk costs prevail and capital stranding is undesirable
- **distributed technologies** — including fuel-passive measures like conventional and transparent insulation
- **heat transport** and **thermal storage** technologies
- **demand management programs** — including adaptive demand control
- **revised system management** protocols and/or objectives

Key features

deeco offers the following important features:

- system purpose is characterized by **exergy-services** supply (see below)
- detrimental and beneficial **dynamic network effects** can be captured
- **temperature-characterized** heat transport and thermal storage are supported
- commodity **storage** and storage **management protocols** are supported
- once the operator proxy (see below) has been selected, all **interventions** are treated *equally*
- plant are aware of their **environment**

Decision support

Results can be presented to decision-makers using trade-off diagrams (see fig 1). Each suite of modifications or *scenario* is normally evaluated in relation to business-as-usual.

Figure 1: Trade-off diagram showing gas turbine options A–C added to an existing 100 MWe cogeneration system. Each option is evaluated under financial cost and CO₂-e minimized system operation — the latter represents a *nonphysical* additionality opportunity.

Model structure

deeco is based on a process/flow model that supports commodity transactions between processes *and* across time. The model is driven by the supply obligations it faces and is managed in accordance with some given definition of best practice.

Exergy is the potential of a commodity to produce work — and is synonymous with "energy" in its everyday sense. Exergy-services are best defined by an appropriate physical intensity: air temperature in the case of space heating/cooling, lux levels for illumination, and so on (intensities do not scale with system size). As a fallback, outright commodity demand can be specified.

Commodities include exergy-carriers like oxidizable fuels, electric power, and transported heat, but the concept also covers instruments such as impact entitlements (resource consents) and emissions permits.

A deeco model consists of the following components:

- a **network structure** — this is an object-oriented representation of the sourcing, conversion, storage, and end-use facilities under consideration, duly connected with regard to commodity type
- a **supply obligation** — to provide exergy-services as specified by time and location

- an **environment** — which establishes the physical and socioeconomic contexts
- a **system operator proxy** — the procedure which determines system activity using flow-based optimization routines and/or prescriptive rules of varying sophistication

Figure 2: A proposed *deeco* model which shows the network structure, supply obligation (indoor temperature), and environmental inputs (insolation, ambient temperature). STI is switchable transparent insulation — an actively-controlled passive solar technology which is still experimental.

deeco treats the system under consideration as a flow network which may be gatewayed to other networks — these necessarily remain outside the jurisdiction of the system operator proxy. *deeco* thus adopts a *distributed planning* ethos.

Individual processes are characterized by flow-defined efficiencies and constraints *and* by state evolution across time — both may depend on ambient conditions. The processes themselves are encapsulated in plant entities which form the building blocks for a *deeco* model.

Whilst no particular cost category is enforced, the following are normally accounted for:

- variable and fixed (levelized) **financial costs**
- resultant **CO₂-e emissions**
- resultant **depletable resource use**
- resultant **air pollution** (various measures)

One cost category is selected as the *objective* for the system operator proxy. The use of variable financial cost equates to short-run marginal cost minimization and best reflects the direct commercial imperative. Other considerations are possible — for instance, oil imports could be tallied and minimized if geopolitical exposure is of concern.

deeco is high-resolution in the following senses:

- **temporal** — the default time-step is one hour and scenarios usually span one year, thereby enabling important daily, weekly, and seasonal variations to be captured
- **topological** — the connectivity of a model can map directly to the architecture of the underlying system, although some aggregation is usually desirable

Supported technologies

The **technology library** contains: conventional furnaces and boilers, conventional thermal power plant, back-pressure and extraction/condensing steam turbines, co-generation plant, gas-motor, electric, and absorption heat-pumps, condensing boilers, heat-exchanger systems for waste heat recovery, short and long-range district heating grids, stratified thermal storage, super-conducting power storage, thermal solar collectors, wind-turbine generators, and photovoltaic panels. Related exergy-carriers include: natural gas, oil, coal, hot water, steam, low-grade heat, electricity, and mechanical power.

Key assumptions

Space precludes a complete list but the two most influential assumptions are:

- selected plant **duties** do not influence the **intensive state** of the system (an orthogonality assumption)
- only certain **efficiency–duty** relationships are possible (a linearity assumption)

Related initiatives

Research initiatives which are similar in terms of model structure and/or application area include: AIM/end-use from the National Institute for Environmental Studies, Japan, the MARKEL/TIMES family coordinated by the IEA, MESSAGE from IIASA, MODEST from the Linköping Institute of Technology, Sweden, PRODesign from the Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands (ECN), and work by Osaka Prefecture University Department of Energy Systems Engineering.

Completed studies

The following studies have been completed and reported:

- **SOLEG** study — design of a solar-supported district heating scheme with seasonal storage (Lindenberger *et al* 2000)
- **ISOTEG** study — modernization of a single-site facility which also considered actively-controlled transparent insulation technologies
- **wind integration** — examination of the effect of sequential wind turbine additions
- **cogeneration upgrade** — analysis of upgrade options which also included amendments to unit commitment policy (fig 1)

Selected publications

- Lindenberger, Dietmar, Thomas Bruckner, Helmuth-M Groscurth, and Reiner Kümmel. 2000. Optimization of solar district heating systems : seasonal storage, heat pumps, and cogeneration. *Energy – The International Journal*. **25**(7): 591–608.
- Bruckner, Thomas, Helmuth-M Groscurth, and Reiner Kümmel. 1997. Competition and synergy between energy technologies in municipal energy systems. *Energy – The International Journal*. **22**(10): 1005–1014
- Groscurth, Helmuth-M, Thomas Bruckner, and Reiner Kümmel. 1995. Modeling of energy-services supply systems. *Energy – The International Journal*. **20**(9): 941–958.

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